

SAMPLE REGISTRATION APP - USER MANUAL

IDRisk

Improving Data quality for RISK assessment

Grant Agreement Number GP/EFSA/ENCO/2018/03

May 2022

App

The Inspector's app, is a Progressive Web Application (PWA), which means it's designed to make the user feels like it's a native application and also, can operate without being connected to the web.

1 Installation

The App can be used either inside a browser or the user can “install” it in his platform. Once the user opens the App page in Chrome, a notification will appear asking if the user desires to install the app (see figs. 1 and 2).

Fig. 1: Icon to install the App

Fig. 2: Confirmation dialogue

An icon will then be installed in the device (fig. 3).

Fig. 3: Installed icon

Once it's installed, the user only has to click the icon, and a window will open the App page, as depicted in fig. 4.

Fig. 4: App opened through the icon

2 Main Menu

The main screen is composed by a four buttons menu (fig. 5). Each operation function is described in table 1.

Fig. 5: Main screen

Button	Description
New	Creates a new operation.
Resume	Resumes any OPEN operation.
Manage	Manages all OPEN / CLOSED operations.
Synchronize	Forces synchronization between the server and the local app.

Tab. 1: Main menu

2.1 New Operation

Once a New Operation is selected (fig. 6), the user must select the form to be used in the operation (fig. 7).

Fig. 6: New Operation

Fig. 7: Form Selection

Note that only forms with the current state as **IN USE** will be listed. In this screen, the user can also print an empty form or export it to pdf.

Once a form is selected, the user will have to fill in the operation details: *name* (mandatory) and *description* (fig. 8).

Fig. 8: Operation details

By pressing Ok, the form will be presented to the user and he can finally start filling it, either in the *Form View* (fig. 9) or in the *List View* (fig. 10). Since both views are synchronized, the user can jump between both views anytime.

Fig. 9: Filling up the form in the Form View

Fig. 10: Filling up the form in the List View

On the top row contains we have a back button, which will take the user back to the details pages. A menu button containing several options (fig. 11), which are described in table 2. The form's name and the operation's name.

Fig. 11: Fill Form menu

Button	Description
Save	Saves the current operation's inputs
Close	Sets the operations OPEN to CLOSED to
Reset	Clears all the inputs
Validate	Validates all inputs according to the rules established in the form (fig. 12)
Print	Prints the form and current inputs (fig. 13)
PDF	Exports the form and current inputs to a PDF file
Annexes	Opens the annexes dialogue, allowing the user to add, remove and download documents, pictures, files, etc. (fig. 14)
Back to Main	Returns the user to the main menu

Tab. 2: Fill form menu descriptions

Fig. 12: Inputs validation

Fig. 13: Printing the form and its inputs

Fig. 14: Operation annexes dialogue

2.2 Resume Operations

Any **OPEN** operation can be resumed by the user at any time. These operations are listed in a table in the Resume Operations screen (fig. 15). A single click or touch will open the selected operation to be edited.

ID	Name	Description	Created in	Form
333	operation name	some description	2021-12-16 15:43:21	Example #1
332	required test		2021-12-14 09:57:30	79f528a-bd28-458e-9752-235e681ab483
197	test 3		2021-11-12 12:23:45	Example #1
196	test 2		2021-11-12 12:21:26	Example #1
195	test 1		2021-11-12 12:18:09	Example #1
182	cxzcxzcx		2021-11-04 09:06:14	assets_test

Fig. 15: Resume operations screen

2.3 Manage Operations

In the operations manager screen (fig. 16), the user can operate on all **OPEN** and **CLOSED** operations.

ID	Name	Description	Date	Status	Operations
333	operation name	some description	2021-12-16 15:43:21	open	🔒 ✓ ✖
332	required test		2021-12-14 09:57:30	open	🔒 ✓ ✖
197	test 3		2021-11-12 12:23:45	open	🔒 ✓ ✖
196	test 2		2021-11-12 12:21:26	open	🔒 ✓ ✖
195	test 1		2021-11-12 12:18:09	open	🔒 ✓ ✖
182	cxzcxzcx		2021-11-04 09:06:14	open	🔒 ✓ ✖
138	operation #1	op1 using form example #1	2021-10-05 14:26:00	closed	🔒 ✓ ✖

Fig. 16: Operations manager screen

There are three global actions:

- Close All – set the status of all operations to **CLOSED**.
- Open All – set the status of all operations to **OPEN**.
- Delete All – deletes all operations.

Each operation also has several actions associated with it (tab.3). Their availability is dependent on the state of the operation.

Button	Action
	Sets to OPEN
	Sets to CLOSED
	Downloads inputs as a json file or as a zip file containing a json file and all input “images” and annexes.
	Validates operation inputs
	Deletes operation

Tab. 3: Possible states of any operation

2.4 Synchronization

For the App to operate when there's not network, the app requires constant synchronization with the server. When the user open the App, it will automatically attempt to synchronize with the server. In this case a visual indication will be presented to the user on this fact (fig. 17).

Fig. 17: App synchronizing

The user also has the option by manually triggering this synchronization by clicking the “Synchronization” button in the main screen. If the App is online, then it will sync, otherwise, it will present a warning message to the user (fig. 18).

Fig. 18: Offline warning

3 Online / Offline Operations

As stated in the previous sections, the App operates both online and offline. For that, is recommended for the user to open its App in network covered place before going to a non-covered place and wait for the synchronization to conclude. This will en-

sure the user will have the most up to date forms and operations in local storage. It also serves as a security measure for any critical incident that can destroy all local records.

All actions are functional, regardless of the network status, so the user doesn't have to worry about the functionality of the operation. However, there is an element that will not work while offline: the map / gps element. So be aware of this restriction.

4 Inputs Validations

When the user validates the inputs, he can be confronted with three types of messages for each input:

OK

WARNING

ERROR

OK means that the input complies with all restrictions, such as, maximum length and right format.

Warning also means that the input complies with all restrictions but it could be better. **Warnings** are usually associated with non-mandatory empty fields.

Error means that at least one restriction is unfulfilled, and the user should correct it, before closing the operation.

Errors / **Warnings**:

- No Value!
- Incorrect format/pattern!
- No uppercase!
- Max length exceed!
- Max value exceeded!
- Min value exceeded!
- No option selected!

5 Printing Notes

While there is no browser recommendation for a good PDF export, on the other hand, for printing a form it's recommended to be performed using the *Chrome* browser. If *Firefox* is used, then it might be required to do minor adjusts to the scale. However this is usually only required for those forms containing *boxes*, *circles* and *lines*.

